

Social Media and Its Impact on the Users

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ABSTRACT

Communication with each other was never so easy. People have moved on from sending letters to mails to now social media which has now a very large platform. The social network platform is helping people to reach each other and with the entire world in a span of a very short time. The large social network is pulling all age groups towards it as, it allows users to be in touch with their friends and get in touch with strangers. The sudden authority of sending and receiving pictures, notes, events, and all the other important and unimportant aspects. Social media users have become externally active on the different sites, but using these sites have positive and negative impact. The study aims to study the kind of impact that users think they have when they use any of the social site.

Keywords: *Social network, Social Media*

Introduction

According to Merriam-Webster, Social media is defined as forms of electronic communication (such as websites for social networking and microblogging) through which users create online communities to share information, ideas, personal messages, and other content (such as videos). Social media got really big in this last 10 years. We started from Orkut, Facebook and now whatsapp, instagram which are allowing us to be in touch with known and unknown people. Few years back people had simple mobile phones which were used only for a simple reason like communication with people. But eventually technology changed and smartphones were introduced with larger capacity and better features. Users of smartphone started downloading social media apps or it allowed people to access websites of all these.

The first recognizable social media site, Six Degrees, was created in 1997. It enabled users to upload a profile and make friends with other users. In 1999, the first blogging sites became popular, creating a social media sensation that's still popular today.

Chaffey (2017) studied that Facebook has 1871 million active users followed by 1000 million users are on whatsapp. Facebook has scored the highest in penetration and engagement. Twitter and instagram are far behind than the other 2 brands.

Review of Literature

Sandra and Nimaz (2016), studied that social media has a tremendous impact on the academic performance of the students. Time appropriateness and health addiction have the largest impact how students perform. Students who are unable to manage time fail to then further meet any given deadline for a particular task.

It also concluded in the paper that time duration and security/privacy problems have minimal or no significant influence on students' academic performance.

Khurana (2015), concluded in the paper that a very big number of users spend more than 2 hours on social sites which actually hampers their social gathering and they prefer sitting at home and surfing net. 73% of respondents said that their work is not affected due to use of these sites as they know the art of putting their priorities first. Users also agreed to the fact as it allows people to do their networking at an extent where it helps their connection.

Chowdhury and Saha (2015), studied that positive

impact of using Facebook that it allows users to connect with their friends, Facebook also allows people to understand the different cultural, social, political point of views. It allowed youngsters to increase their creativity. Few negative impacts are the users spend lot of time on using media. It reduces the time that they spent on reading and doing other creative things. excess information which is revealed can also be harmful and can breach the privacy.

Amedie (2015), summarized in the paper that social media allows users to create false identities and superficial connections, causes depression and is a primary recruiting tool of criminals and terrorists. Social media is one of the many sources of emotional issues.

A.T.M Shahjahan, Kutub Uddin Chisty (2014), stated few positive and negative impact on users. Few stated are as meeting new people, sharing ideas beyond a particular state or a country 3. Reducing travelling costs, costs of buying books 4. Expansion of democratic space. 5. You can pass a message to your friends to maintain peace in your society 6. Reaching maximum people for the business purpose. And the negative impact discussed are that people tend to discuss their and others personal issues on the media without the consent. Family ties usually go weak as more time is spent on the media and not on the relationship.

Aida Abdulahi et al (2014) studied that highest contributor which is protection and security issues have a critical positive relationship. The importance of this is the utilization of Facebook increment, the measure of introduction to protection and security issues increments too. Scholarly execution has a negative critical relationship. This implies when the reliant variable increment, the autonomous variable lessening. In this investigation, when an informal communication site is utilized as often as possible the scholastic execution of understudies diminish. Besides, the wellbeing danger result demonstrates that there is a little association with informal community site

Objectives

1. To study the reasons of using social media
2. To study the impact on personal life of social media

Limitations of Study

1. This study is purely based on the information sourced from the social media users from of one

college in Pune.

2. The study is conducted in the current scenario and the opinions, perception and expectations of the respondents may differ with time.

3. The study is purely on the basis of the sample. The sample's limitations in terms of their maturity, understanding and exposure.

Research Mythology

The questionnaire was sent online to all the social media users, and the online responses were collected. Total of 50 samples were collected and further analyzed, secondary data was collected from the various websites and online research portals.

Analysis and Interpretation

The analysis showed that 100% respondents were using whatapp followed by 85% Facebook users. The least popular currently amongst all these is Twitter.

Social media users are spending 02-04 hours daily, followed by 20% users are using 01-02 hours and 30 mines each

The major reason behind social media users are connecting with current friends followed by professional work.

Social media users prefer connecting with friends which is 68% and then followed by 21 % who like connecting with strangers.

61 % Social media users said that there is no effect on their personal life because of using the any of the above social site.

34% social media users said that the impact of using social media is positive, and 46% users are neutral about it.

The respondents said that the major impact is fast interaction followed by fast sharing, learning and research capabilities.

46% of users said that they can stay without using the social media for less than a week, followed by 17 %

users who can stay away for maximum 2 days.

Suggestions and Conclusion

1. Maximum social media users are on whatapp, followed by Facebook. Indian company Hike and a very famous US brand twitter are yet to gain the market as big as other top 2 brands.
2. Maximum time spent by the users on the media is 02 to 04 hours, and they can stay without going on these sites for less than a week.
3. The larger number of users said that they are neutral about the impact of social network on their personal life.
4. Larger percentage of users said that the use of all these apps or website is for connecting with friends followed by professional work.
5. Respondents who thinks that there is an impact they say fast interaction followed by fast sharing, learning and research capabilities.
6. The author suggests that the websites can be used for more of learning and spreading awareness about issues which are not reaching the right market.

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